

Tracing Inadequacies in Municipal Solid Waste Infrastructure and Mapping Climate Change Risks

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Abstract

Urban development is stalled when solid waste management (SWM) is not kept at the centre of institutional and community action. The onus of the multi-staged SWM in India, lies on Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) who have to plan for its management from the generation to disposal – all these duties, when imagined as interlinked, moving parts of the overall SWM system, sit atop (and are contingent on) a physical layer – *infrastructure*. A comprehensive synthesis of information, specifically an analysis of infrastructure-derived leakages across the waste value chain, is currently absent in the Indian urban context. Furthermore, infrastructure, with its long gestation periods and longer permanence, is usually planned for the present. Climate change brings with it a shift in reality, wherein the infrastructure planned today will still be operational when climate risks intensify – the integration of a climate risk lens into such an analysis has not yet been systematically undertaken. This research addresses both these gaps.

A value chain analysis as a mode of inquiry for MSWI reveals that every stage of waste management, from generation to disposal, has infrastructural deficits. It also reveals that if these gaps are plugged, disproportionately positive outcomes can be achieved. Climate Change has transformed the way systems function and interact – the same applies to the MSWI system. Integrating the climate change lens to waste infrastructure planning, design and operations is the need of the hour. The research aimed to unearth the weak spots in the municipal solid waste infrastructure which lead to suboptimal outcomes. The findings, synthesised stage-wise, conveys the visual of a fragmented system. It also provides a semblance of an action plan – addressing these known gaps across urban jurisdictions, can become the initial steps towards reforming (albeit incrementally) the MSWI system.

Key words: Municipal Solid Waste Infrastructure, Waste Infrastructure, Climate Risk, Climate Resilience, Solid Waste Management, India

Introduction

Background

Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) as a category of waste refers to the refuse originating from primarily four sectors: residential, commercial, institutional, and industrial. Compositionally, they comprise of recyclables (like, paper, glass, plastics, metals), organics (biodegradable waste like food and garden waste) and residuals (non-recyclable, non-compostable) (Z. Gueboudji et al., 2024). The presence of multiple types of waste streams under a singular MSW umbrella illustrates the complexity of management of MSW, especially since its mismanagement has implications for public health, sanitation, environmental health, and land utilisation, among others.

Some statistics help contextualise the problem and highlight the quantum of waste generated in urban India – 62 million tonnes per year of MSW is currently generated in urban areas, with a projected increase to 165 million tonnes and 436 million tonnes by the year 2030 and 2050, respectively (Raj et al., 2024). More than 10,000 hectares of urban land, with land being a finite resource, is ‘locked up’ as legacy landfills and waste dumpsites. Emissions from solid waste (without any considerable improvement in the existing system) will come to about 2.6 billion tonnes of CO₂ equivalent by 2050. Public health is affected (vector-borne diseases emerging from waste hotspots), animal health is another casualty (animals feeding on waste dumps) and drains are clogged, potentially leading to urban flooding (Central Public Health and Environmental Engineering Organisation (CPHEEO), 2020).

Urban development is stalled when solid waste management (SWM) is not kept at the centre of institutional and community action, is what this scenario alludes to. The onus of Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) in India lies on the city-specific Urban Local Bodies (ULBs). These ULBs have the onerous task of operationalising (and ensuring the cost-effectiveness of) the waste value chain, with varied responsibilities – collection and transportation (C&T), ensuring the waste remains segregated (before that, creating systems for source segregation), constructing material recovery facilities (MRFs) and recycling centres, treating and disposing waste, and scientifically managing landfills, among other priorities (Zhu et al., 2007). All these duties, when imagined as interlinked, moving parts of the overall SWM system, sit atop (and are contingent on) a physical layer – *infrastructure*.

The research layer – Municipal Solid Waste Infrastructure

Put simply, according to Liu et al. (2023) Municipal Solid Waste Infrastructure (MSWI) is a “*series of facilities that collect and treat MSW*”, and is the “*underlying hardware*” of logistical complexities – integral to effectuate a circular economy in waste management. Liu et al. (2023) envision MSWI as an amalgamation of social and technical systems, where “*several chained or parallel MSW treatment subsystems*” interact dynamically. The interaction between ‘physical facilities’ (man-made, tangible, physical infrastructure) and ‘actors’ (civil, public and private) is influenced by the external environment, consisting of rules, laws, policies, regulations, the local culture, and the level of technological development.

Infrastructure is an important element to consider when conceptualising any plan for waste management, since it influences urban circularity and inclusiveness. Waste infrastructure plays a symbolic role in the form of a behavioral nudge and also impacts segregation and sorting efficacy at the community level. Waste recycling behaviors are enhanced and maintained, becoming a part of the ‘community culture’, when modern waste separation and recycling facilities are made available at higher density and at appropriate locations. Poorly maintained waste collection facilities discourage waste recycling behaviors (Liu et al., 2023).

The social acceptance of waste infrastructure (siting of waste infrastructure is a politically contested topic, with the ‘not in my backyard syndrome’ afflicting the process) is dependent on local culture and community’s environmental awareness levels. According to Liu et al. (2023) MSWI also has a transformative potential, in that it “*reshapes the scale and pathways of waste streams, ... influencing the value derived from or impacted by different actors.*”

Furthermore, the discourse around MSWI often runs the risk of emphasising upon centralised, state-controlled facilities, ignoring the importance of informal MSW processing facilities which are borne out of community-led social innovation enterprises – community composters and small scrapyards, for example. The Dry Waste Collection Centres (DWCCs) in the wards of Bengaluru, as a novel partnership model and led by Hasiru Dala, where the entire dry waste management of the city is given to waste pickers (formalisation of the informal) and women self-help groups (SHGs), is another case in point. It is imperative for urban policymakers to recognise the contribution of these non-formalised entities, and ensure their integration in the overall MSWI system (Hasiru Dala, n.d.; Liu et al., 2023).

Motivation

Leakages in the waste supply chain, seen through the infrastructural lens, serve as an important scope of inquiry. A mapping of MSWI will allow unearthing of the gaps in existing waste value chains, and provide insights to ULBs about the gaps in provisioning of waste management services. ‘Infrastructure’ (alongside, ‘attitude and awareness’ and ‘policy-governance’), as recognised by Khan et al. (2025), is a root cause of ineffectiveness of waste management strategies. They cite the “*lack of effective management information systems, appropriate vehicles for waste collection and transportation, and waste storage areas. ... unreliable power supply and poorly designed facilities,*” as barriers to progress. Thus, mapping all these infrastructural issues will help shed light on the weak spots present in the current systems.

Extending the research layer: Climate resilience of Solid Waste Infrastructure

Building on the research layer of MSWI, an added dimension of inquiry emerges in the form of climate risks to this infrastructure. Solid Waste and climate change have a bilateral relationship, where climate extremities like urban flooding and extreme heat act as potential sources of damage to waste infrastructure, on the one hand, while SWM (through reducing methane and other Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emissions) can play a key role in climate change mitigation (Asian Development Bank, 2023).

Infrastructure, with its long gestation periods and longer permanence, is usually planned for the present. Climate change brings with it a shift in reality, wherein the infrastructure planned today will still be operational when climate risks intensify. *Figure 1* illustrates this overlap. On a 100 year operational timeline, waste infrastructure lifelines vary – Compost facilities, and Material Recovery Facilities, for example, will last for 20 years, Advanced Thermal Treatment (ATT) facilities and their 40-50 years lifelines, and finally, landfills with their 100 year permanence. The lower part of the illustration provides climate change projections, and aligns it with the infrastructure life cycles. Superimposing these projections – a 2°C warming scenario “very likely” within 20-40 years, a 4°C increase in the next 60-80 years, and a likely one metre rise in sea levels within 60-80 years – on the infrastructure timelines, reveal a growing overlap between infrastructure operation and climate risk. Already existing infrastructure (built during a different climatic reality) will continue to operate in a riskier scenario and therefore, require requires a new design thinking approach (with a climate lens) towards the planning of new waste infrastructure, while parallely focusing on retrofitting existing infrastructure, is the conclusion that can be drawn.

Figure 1

Approximate lifetimes (in years) of waste infrastructure facilities, compared with illustrative climate change timescales

Adapted from Winne et al. (2012)

Knowledge Gaps

A comprehensive synthesis of information, specifically an analysis of infrastructure-derived leakages across the waste value chain, is currently absent in the Indian urban context. Furthermore, the integration of a climate risk lens into such an analysis has not yet been systematically undertaken. This research attempts to address these gaps by combining both, timely, dimensions – mapping solid waste mismanagement hotspots across the waste value chain and underscoring the climate vulnerability of such infrastructure.

Aim: *To map the inefficiencies of physical waste infrastructure across the Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) value chain in Indian cities, through a climate resilience lens.*

Objectives

1. Map the physical waste infrastructure required across all stages of the waste value chain – from generation to disposal.

2. Identify gaps in infrastructure provisioning which lead to ineffective SWM outcomes.
3. Integrate a climate resilience lens into waste infrastructure mapping.
4. Position the synthesised information as a foundational layer to be fed into the development of a ward-specific MSWI framework.

Methods

The study involves secondary research, specifically a desk-review with a qualitative, descriptive design. The research aims to synthesize existing knowledge giving emphasis on grey literature sources, like Indian think tank reports, government reports and toolkits, and journal articles for formulation of the concluding framework.

The interpretation of literature will aim to extract the following key categories of information: Physical infrastructure needed to address solid waste management, waste mismanagement hotspots and high leakage points, climate vulnerability of waste infrastructure under extreme heat and urban flooding scenarios, strategies, fixes and design considerations for retrofitting and planning future infrastructure.

Search Strings

“Informal Waste Sector Infrastructure” “Solid Waste Management Plan” “Solid Waste Infrastructure Mapping” “Waste Flow Mapping” “Garbage Vulnerable Points and waste” “System Maps for Solid Waste” “Guidance Documents for Waste Management” “Climate resilience of Waste Infrastructure” “Climate risks and Waste Infrastructure” “Climate Change adaptation and Waste Infrastructure”

Selection process

Google Scholar and Google search engine, are the primary databases used for extraction of literature. Title, abstracts and full texts are screened manually by the researcher.

Inclusion Criteria

- Relevance to MSW Infrastructure (formal/informal/visible/invisible)
- Focus on the Indian context or transferable insights
- Types of documents: Think tank reports, guidance documents released by governmental bodies, performance audit reports, journal articles, news media reports, anecdotal insights.

- Language: English

Results

Table 1

Root cause identification of solid waste management inadequacies

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Table 1 shows the results gained from a desk review of literature, and is divided on the basis of the waste value chain. The following emerge as the key insights:

A. Waste Generation

The root cause analysis undertaken by Khan et al. (2025) reveal that at the outset of the lifecycle of solid waste, open dumping persists owing to a lack of primary infrastructure (dustbins) and information asymmetry (lack of information about dumping points). This is further exacerbated by non-uniform colour coding of dustbins across jurisdictions – leading to confusion over segregation, “fracturing” the SWM system in the very beginning itself (NITI Aayog, 2021). Otitoju & Seng (2014) shed light on the design aspect stating that attractive designs of dustbins and recycling centres improve compliance.

The Navi Mumbai Municipal Corporation (NMMC), in an attempt towards visibilising primary waste infrastructure and improving compliance against open dumping, presents a practical intervention by converting garbage vulnerable points (GVPs) into green zones (Khan et al., 2025).

B. Waste Collection

The next stage is afflicted with a different set of issues with a common theme emerging – low or non-maintenance of collection vehicles and inappropriate design of vehicles incongruent to the type of waste stream, especially hazardous domestic waste. The collection efficiency is hindered, and the lack of compartments in such vehicles lead to waste getting mixed (segregation is lost). Indore Municipal Corporation (IMC) has mandated its primary collection vehicles to be compartmentalised in six parts – dry, wet, plastic, sanitary, domestic hazardous and e-waste. Such uniformity in policy mandates, complemented with compliance and proper implementation, is integral across Indian cities to create effective SWM systems. Additionally, unequal service coverage in urban slums (and consequent, garbage vulnerable points or ‘GVPs’) requires contextually relevant infrastructural innovations – IMC’s customised hand carts for narrow lanes, being one such illustration (Khan et al., 2025).

C. Waste Transportation

Vehicular problems and lack of decentralisation are the two themes which emerge at the transportation stage of MSW. Lack of preventative maintenance of transportation vehicles, and their poor condition exacerbated by equally poor road infrastructure, result in their frequent breakdown. As for the latter, growing urbanisation has resulted in an increase in distance between waste collection points and treatment facilities – centralisation which creates more leakage points for waste during its transportation before treatment. It is in this context that Surat Municipal Corporation’s ward-wise mapping of waste streams and aligning them to their respective transfer stations, and focus on keeping the separation of wet and dry waste at the transfer stations intact, makes for a replicable solution (Khan et al., 2025).

D. Waste Treatment

Khan et al. (2025) highlight a lack of operation and maintenance of waste treatment facilities and a lack of investment in pre-processing infrastructure as infrastructural deficits derailing SWM. Pre-processing infrastructure is needed for dust removal, shredding, dry and bailing of collected waste and improves its quality – encouraging circular economy principles. The authors also bring attention to the political nature of siting of waste infrastructure in stating that constructing waste treatment facilities often involves a complex set of approvals – acquisition of land clearances and approval of nearby residents (“not-in-my-backyard” syndrome, potentially hampering siting).

An emerging infrastructural focus is that of Dry Waste Collection Centres (DWCCs). Qabeer (2019) finds that despite this new model of segregation and recycling, these centres are often constructed using substandard materials and their resultant poor structural integrity not only has adverse implications for waste management, but also increases cost because of rebuilding post ruin. Roof leakages are also common, which pose an additional cost due to damage done to high value recyclables.

E. Waste Disposal

Foul odour and fires at disposal facilities in landfills is a common occurrence, as highlighted by Khan et al. (2025). Lack of segregation and ingress of mixed waste in landfill areas lead to leachate seeping and degradation of natural resources (soil and water). Therefore, the authors underscore the need for rainsheds, leachate treatment plants and proper storage for untreated (mixed) waste as essential infrastructural needs at the waste disposal stage.

Table 2

High Leakage Points of Solid Waste, with an infrastructural focus

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Table 2 is a compilation of high leakage points, which if addressed, can help plug in important gaps in the MSWI system. GIZ et al. (2020), from a physical infrastructural perspective, allude to five such categories – as Table 2 illustrates.

Collection containers without lids or with gaps in the side become easily accessible to animals – same is the case with collection vehicles, which also often exhibit a discrepancy between intended capacity and load. The authors call for fully enclosed vehicles, like compactor trucks and mapping of waste flows so that the corresponding data can help alleviate the capacity vs load discrepancy. Multiple handling and manual loading of waste from one vehicle to another – using shovels, wheelbarrows or other machinery – also leads to waste leaking from the value chain. Here, automatic systems for loading where the waste does not have to change hands, rather the containers are moved directly to the collection vehicle, keeps the waste intact. Longer waiting times at transferring stations and just the deficit in the number of such decentralised stations, contribute to this high leakage potential.

Table 3

Effects of Climate Change on Waste Infrastructure

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Owing to the contemporaneous nature of climate change with infrastructure planning, construction and operation, Table 3 provides a glimpse of how climate risks, specifically extreme heat and urban flooding, can adversely impact solid waste infrastructure.

Extreme heat affects the waste value chain by overheating collection vehicles and sorting equipment, expediting the decomposition process of organic waste (and consequently, odour and pest issues) and increases the occurrence of landfill fires and fires at waste hotspots. Urban flooding, on the other hand, damages low-lying waste processing facilities and can also lead to increased instances of waste leachate seeping into the soil and nearby water bodies, and also washing waste onto the streets. A related impact is on waste transportation where collection routes get waterlogged during flooding, impacting collection efficiency and transportation

infrastructure negatively (C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group, 2020; United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2023).

The authors suggest adaptation steps such as – increasing the cooling capacity of waste infrastructure, enclosing collection vehicles, focusing on decentralised facilities and reworking collection time schedules to circumvent the problem of faster decomposition of waste due to heat. Identification of alternative routes for collection and transportation of waste for mitigating the effects of urban flooding, is also suggested (C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group, 2020; United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2023).

Discussion

A value chain analysis as a mode of inquiry for MSWI reveals that every stage of waste management, from generation to disposal, has infrastructural deficits. It also reveals that if these gaps are plugged, disproportionately positive outcomes can be achieved. The following key themes emerged from the literature review:

A. Design and data – two pillars for effective infrastructural planning

Otitiju & Seng (2014) found that having attractive designs for separation bins and recycling centres, incentives a pro-segregation behaviour among urban residents. High visibility of primary infrastructure, like curbside dustbins, in the same vein, becomes an important infrastructural priority. Design as a priority, is also echoed by Khan et al. (2025) – vehicle design should cater to local solid waste composition and flows. and design of transfer stations should ensure that wet and dry waste remain separated. Even Dry Waste Collection Centres (DWCCs) need to integrate a human centred design (HCD) and climate risk lens, to ensure waste workers' working conditions are optimal and dignified, and the quality of waste collected is not damaged due to extreme weather conditions (Qabeer, 2019). The lack of lids in collection containers further highlights the absence of design thinking in infrastructure planning (GIZ et al., 2020).

Design, therefore, is an indispensable tool when any strategy for SWM is to be conceptualised. For design to work, data is an important accompanying factor – mapping waste flows at the ward-level, will help, for example when planning for customised waste vehicles, as Khan et al. (2025) state.

B. Decentralisation

Another emerging theme is the call for decentralised infrastructure. Longer distances between collection and treatment points, poor road conditions exacerbated by extreme climatic conditions, and multiple handling being high leakage points, all together make the case for planning for more local infrastructure (GIZ et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2025). Flexible financial instruments for financing such decentralised infrastructure and incentives for adoption by municipalities, along with support from civil society organisations – as is the model of Hasiru Dala – becomes a policy priority.

C. Non-waste infrastructure as a complementary policy priority

The studies also offer a glimpse into the important role non-waste infrastructure plays in the overall MSWI system. As *Figure 1* shows, transport, energy, water and built infrastructure are and will be affected by climate change risks. Waste infrastructure does not function in a vacuum. Poor quality roads damage waste transportation vehicles. Waste treatment facilities run the risk of overheating during extreme heat conditions in the absence of sustainable cooling capacities – energy and waste infrastructure intersection emerges here (Winne et al., 2012). Recognising this interconnectedness, as these examples showcase, when planning and siting infrastructure is necessary.

D. Climate Change as a structural barrier to waste management

Systems respond to change. Climate Change has transformed the way systems function and interact – the same applies to the MSWI system. This recognition has become foundational to any infrastructural planning, and as the previous sections showed, needs intervention at all stages of the waste value chain.

Further, adaptation to adverse climate impacts is contingent on funds – the potential cost of making waste infrastructure climate resilient can prove to be an inhibitor. Winne et al. (2012) have given a three staged implementation plan, from low to high cost, for integrating climate resilience consideration in waste infrastructure design, planning and operations.

I. The immediate, lowest cost plan entails raising awareness about specific climate risks, strengthening local partnerships for integrated climate response, updating regulations, policies and procurement processes mandating resilience planning (like, infrastructure siting in non-floodplain locations, adding extra storage, including climate lens in project planning, etc.).

II. Stage 2 talks about early adaptation activities where designing ‘flexible’ and portable waste infrastructure and consequently, system – here, alternative access routes, and cooling options for vehicles and waste facilities, etc., are considered.

III. The long term, higher cost adaptation investments (Stage 3) include site-specific technology upgrades and engineering solutions and embedding climate risk assessments early on during procurement and project design.

Conclusion

Integrating the climate change lens to waste infrastructure planning, design and operations is the need of the hour. To achieve that, a climate risk and vulnerabilities assessment of SWM infrastructure should be the first step. Cities, at the micro level (ward), need to identify potential scenarios of climate extremities in their region, and develop a climate resilience plan for MSWIS, where effective stakeholder engagement (the ‘social’ waste infrastructure) proves key (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2023).

Vulnerability mapping for current and future vulnerability of waste infrastructure to physical climate impacts, becomes important from the standpoint of research and data collection. From the policy angle, the formulation of a guidance document for site operators, procurement agencies, local authorities and other waste infrastructure stakeholders on practical ways to adapt to climate change, can be undertaken, with a thrust on developing ward-level screening tool for vulnerability assessment at site level (Winne et al., 2012).

The research aimed to unearth the weak spots in the municipal solid waste infrastructure which lead to suboptimal outcomes. The findings, synthesised stage-wise, conveys the visual of a fragmented system. It also provides a semblance of an action plan – addressing these known gaps across urban jurisdictions, can become the initial steps towards reforming (albeit incrementally) the MSWI system.

Future Directions

The rationale of this research was to make a case for including an infrastructure-focus lens while formulating a ward-level plan for SWM. Further, it also sheds light on the importance of integrating a climate risk lens to MSWIS.

Figure 2, has been adapted from Liu et al. (2023)'s conceptualisation of the MSWI as a complex interaction of technical and social subsystems. The orange dotted line, and the components in the figure differ from the original MSWIS, which the authors of the paper had made for Almere. Based on the insights gathered from this secondary research, the figure has been modified to include some components to the technical layer, with the orange dotted lines alluding to the larger systemic effect of climate change on the MSWIS.

Since the current research was limited to secondary resources, and was limited in its scope – the social subsystem part of the MSWIS was left untouched. The informal and formal waste worker economy is an indispensable part of any SWM strategy, and the conception of the plan – without considering the inputs of the infrastructure operators – makes for an incomplete story. Future research should aim to complement this lens with human accounts of those who are behind this physical infrastructure, and the ways climate mitigation can take shape keeping into consideration, the working conditions of the workers who make up the social infrastructure of SWM.

The social layer also includes the role of municipalities, civil society and policymakers – who influence MSWIS and vice versa. The mapping of physical infrastructure was just the first step. The figure is a useful tool to envision the interacting elements of SWM and plan for a holistic waste management strategy, as is intended for the Marappanapalya ward.

Figure 2

Subsystems of the Municipal Solid Waste Infrastructure (MSWI) System. Adapted from (Liu et al., 2023)

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